

Heterocyclic Systems with Bridgehead Nitrogen Atom : Reactions of 4-amino-5-mercapto-3-substituted-*s*-triazoles with Haloketones, Carboxylic acids and α -halo acids

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The reaction of 4-amino-5-mercapto-3-substituted-*s*-triazoles(I) with chloranil and α -haloketones furnished 3, 10-disubstituted-6, 13-dichloro, *bis*(*s*-triazolo[3,4:2',3'] [1,3,4] thiadiazino[5',6'-b:5',6'-e] cyclohexa-1,4-diene(II) and 7*H*-3,6-disubstituted-*s*-triazolo[3,4-*b*][1,3,4] thiadiazoles(III) respectively. Similarly reaction of I with aromatic carboxylic acids and oxalic acid in presence of phosphorous oxychloride gave *s*-triazolo [3,4-*b*][1,3,4] thiadiazoles(IV) and 6,6'-*bis*(3,6-diphenyl-*s*-triazolo [3,4-*b*][1,3,4] thiadiazoles(V) respectively, whereas with α -chloroacetic acid afforded 7*H*-3-phenyl-*s*-triazolo [3,4-*b*][1,3,4] thiadiazin 6(5*H*)-one(VI). Some of the compounds were screened for their antitumor activity.

IN continuation to our work on the syntheses of Bridgehead nitrogen heterocycles¹⁻⁴, the present communication deals with the syntheses of some new 3,10-disubstituted-6, 13-dichloro-*bis*(*s*-triazolo [3,4:2',3'] [1,3,4] thiadiazino[5',6'-b:5',6'-e] cyclohexa-1,4-dienes(II), 3, 6-disubstituted-*s*-triazolo [3,4-*b*][1,3,4] thiadiazoles(III), *s*-triazolo[3,4-*b*][1,3,4] thiadiazoles(IV), 6,6'-*bis*(3,6-diphenyl-*s*-triazolo[3,4-*b*][1,3,4] thiadiazole(V) and 7*H*-3-phenyl-*s*-triazolo[3,4-*b*][1,3,4]-thiadiazin 6(5*H*)-one(VI) respectively. Thus I when condensed with chloranil in presence of fused sodium acetate and anhydrous ethanol yielded II, whereas with α -haloketones furnished III. *s*-Triazolo [3,4-*b*][1,3,4] thiadiazoles have been synthesized by Golgolab *et al*⁵. I when reacted with aromatic carboxylic acids and oxalic acid in presence of phosphorous oxychloride gave IV and V respectively. Reaction of I (R=C₆H₅) with mono-chloro-acetic acid in presence of anhydrous sodium acetate and absolute alcohol furnished(VI). The spectral character of compounds II, III, IV, V and VI are also consistent with the structures proposed for them (vide experimental).

1. Chloranil, EtOH, NaOAc ;
2. R₁COCH₂X, EtOH, NaOAc ;
3. R₁COOH, POCl₃ ;
4. Oxalic acid, POCl₃ &
5. ClCH₂COOH, EtOH, NaOAc.

*For Correspondence.

Compounds II (R=CH₃, C₂H₅, *o*-HO-C₆H₄) and III (R=*o*-HO-C₆H₄, R₁=C₆H₅-C₆H₄; R=CH₃, R₁=C₆H₅-C₆H₄; R=C₂H₅, R₁=C₆H₅-C₆H₄) have been screened for their biological evaluation as possible anticancer agents. However none of the compounds showed any significant activity when tested against P 388 lymphocytic leukemia *in vivo*.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. IR spectra were taken on Beckman I.R.-20 spectrophotometer in Nujol mull.

3-*o*-Hydroxyphenyl-4-amino-5-mercapto-*s*-triazole (I, R=*o*-HO-C₆H₄):

This was prepared by heating under reflux *o*-hydroxy benzoyl-dithiocarbazine (5.32 g, 0.02 mole) and hydrazine-hydrate 80% (10 ml) for about two hours. The colour of the reaction mixture changed to green, hydrogen sulphide was evolved resulting in a homogeneous solution. The reaction mixture was cooled, diluted with water and neutralized with conc. HCl. The white precipitate thus obtained was filtered, washed with water and crystallized from aqueous ethanol in colourless needles. m.p. 208-09°. Yield 60% (2.5 g). I.R. ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹) 3290, 3080, 1630, 1580, 1495, 1160, 1020, 760, 690 (Found: S, 14.96. C₈H₈N₄SO requires S, 15.38%).

3-Phenyl-4-amino-5-mercapto-*s*-triazole(I, R=C₆H₅):

It was prepared by the method of Reid and Heindel⁶.

3-Alkyl substituted-4-amino-5-mercapto-s-triazoles :

These were synthesized by refluxing a mixture of thiocarbohydrazide and the corresponding aliphatic acids as described in the literature^{7,8}.

3-10-Diethyl-6,13-dichloro-bis(*s*-triazolo [3,4 : 2',3'] [1,3,4] thiadiazino [5',6'-b : 5',6'-e] Cyclohexa-1,4-diene (II, R=C₂H₅) :

I (R=C₂H₅, 2.88 g, 0.02 mole), chloranil (2.46 g, 0.01 mole) and anhydrous sodium acetate (1.64 g) in absolute ethanol (40 ml) were refluxed on a steam bath for about 4 hours. The reaction mixture acquired reddish colouration and a red coloured solid separated. The solid was filtered, washed thoroughly with water and a small amount was crystallized from DMF. m.p. > 300°. Yield (58%). ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹) 1650, 1535, 1150, 955, 835, 720 (Found : C, 39.88; H, 2.52; S, 14.86. C₁₄H₁₀N₈S₂Cl₂ requires C, 39.53; H, 2.35; S, 15.06%).

The other similar compounds prepared are below in Table 1.

TABLE 1—3,10-DISUBSTITUTED-6,13-DICHLORO-bis(*s*-TRIAZOLO[3,4 : 2',3'] [1,3,4]THIADIAZINO[5',6'-b : 5',6'-e] CYCLOHEXA-1,4-DIENE(II)

R	m.p. °C	Yield
H	> 300	50
C ₂ H ₅	292-35	64
C ₆ H ₅	> 290	80
<i>o</i> -HO-C ₆ H ₄	> 300	75

7H-3(*o*-Hydroxyphenyl)-6-biphenyl-*s*-triazolo[3,4-*b*] [1,3,4]thiadiazine(III, R=*o*-HO-C₆H₄, R₁=C₆H₅-C₆H₄) :

I (R=HO-C₆H₄, 1.04 g, 0.005 mole), *p*-phenyl phenacyl bromide (1.38 g, 0.005 mole) and fused sodium acetate (0.5 g) in anhydrous ethanol (30 ml) was refluxed for about seven hours. The solid obtained on cooling was filtered, washed thoroughly with water and crystallized from acetic acid. m.p. 230°. Yield 1.6 g (80%). ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹), 3500-3400, 1630, 1590, 1490, 1265, 830, 745, 700 (Found : S, 7.97; N, 14.14. C₂₂H₁₆N₄SO requires S, 8.33; N, 14.58%).

The properties and analyses of other *s*-triazolo-thiadiazines(III) are described in Table 2.

3-Phenyl-6-*p*-nitrophenyl-*s*-triazolo [3,4-*b*] [1,3,4] thiadiazole (IV, R=C₆H₅, R₁=*p*-O₂N-C₆H₄) :

A mixture of I, (R=C₆H₅, 0.96 g, 0.005 mole), *p*-nitro benzoic acid (1.67 g, 0.01 mole) and phosphorous oxychloride (10 ml) was refluxed for about one hour. The reaction mixture poured over crushed ice. The solid thus separated was filtered

TABLE 2—7H-3,6-DIARYL-*s*-TRIAZOLO[3,4-*b*][1,3,4]-THIADIAZINES (III, R *o*-HO-C₆H₄)

R ₁	m.p. °C	Yield %
C ₆ H ₅	212	71
<i>p</i> -Br-C ₆ H ₄	292	64
<i>m</i> -O ₂ N-C ₆ H ₄	265-70*	56
3,4(HO) ₂ C ₆ H ₃	252-55*	67
<i>p</i> -Cl-C ₆ H ₄	242	67

* Charring takes place.

and treated with dilute sodium hydroxide solution to remove unreacted materials. Again filtered, washed with water and finally crystallized from acetic acid. m.p. 261°. Yield 1.40 g (86%). ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹), 1610, 1525, 1350, 970, 850, 770, 685 (Found : S, 9.53, C₁₄H₈N₆SO₂ requires S, 9.91%).

The other *s*-triazolothiadiazoles prepared in this connection are given in Table 3.

TABLE 3—3,6-DISUBSTITUTED-*s*-TRIAZOLO [3,4-*b*][1,3,4]-THIADIAZINES(IV)

R	R ₁	m.p. °C	Yield %
C ₆ H ₅	<i>m</i> -O ₂ NC ₆ H ₄	219	68
C ₆ H ₅	3,5(O ₂ N) ₂ C ₆ H ₃	> 290	88
C ₆ H ₅	<i>o</i> -Cl-C ₆ H ₄	188	71
C ₆ H ₅	<i>p</i> -Cl-C ₆ H ₄	194	76
C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅ -OH=CH	182-83	85
CH ₃	<i>p</i> -O ₂ N-C ₆ H ₄	262	69
OH	3,5(O ₂ N) ₂ C ₆ H ₃	255	65
OH	<i>p</i> -Cl-C ₆ H ₄	195	73

Bis-(3-phenyl-*s*-triazolo[3,4-*b*][1,3,4]-thiadiazole) (V) :

This was synthesized by reacting a mixture of I (R=C₆H₅, 3.84 g, 0.02 mole), oxalic acid (1.26 g, 0.01 mole) and phosphorous oxychloride (15 ml) following the above procedure. m.p. > 300° (acetic acid). Yield 45%. ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹), 1600, 1525, 960, 900, 760, 680 (Found : S, 15.71; N, 27.38. C₁₈H₁₀N₈S₂ requires S, 15.92; N, 27.86%).

7H-3-Phenyl-*s*-triazolo [3,4-*b*][1,3,4] thiadiazino-6 (5H)-one(VI) :

I (R=C₆H₅, 1.92 g, 0.01 mole), chloroacetic acid (1.0 g, 0.01 mole) and fused sodium acetate (0.82 g) taken in anhydrous ethanol (30 ml) were refluxed on a steam bath for 6 hours. The reaction mixture poured over water. The white solid filtered and crystallized from ethanol in colourless crystals, m.p. 185-86°. Yield 1.2 g (51.7%). ν_{\max} cm⁻¹ 3340, 3270, 1720, 1610, 1520, 1350, 1200, 970, 890, 775, 690 (Found : S, 13.42; N, 23.86. C₁₀H₈N₄SO requires S, 13.79; N, 24.14%).

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References

1. V. K. CHADHA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **55**, 817.
2. V. K. CHADHA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **54**, 878.
3. J. MOHAN, V. K. CHADHA, K. S. SHARMA and H. K. PUJARI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1976, **14B**, 723.
4. R. P. GUPTA, L. L. SACHDEVA, K. S. DHAKA, V. K. CHADHA and H. K. PUJARI, *Ann. Soc. Sci. Bruxelles*, 1979, **T93**, 137.
5. H. GOLGOLAB, I. LALEZARI and L. HOSSEINI-GOHARI, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1973, **10**, 387.
6. J. R. REID and N. D. HEINDRI, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1976, **13**, 925.
7. H. SCIKACHI and M. KANOKA, *Yakugaku Zasshi*, 1962, **82**, 683; *Chem. Abs.*, 1963, **58**, 4543.
8. K. S. DHAKA, J. MOHAN, V. K. CHADHA and H. K. PUJARI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1974, **12**, 287.